

RT-OCR : Real-Time OCR Pipeline with Formal Timing Guarantees for Edge Vision Systems

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Abstract Deep learning OCR achieves high accuracy but exhibits unpredictable latency, preventing deployment in safety-critical systems like autonomous vehicles and industrial robotics. RT-OCR provides formal worst-case execution time (WCET) bounds on edge platforms through a timing-aware pipeline architecture, adaptive workload controller, and measurement-based WCET characterization on Jetson Nano and Raspberry Pi 5. Evaluation demonstrates 73% jitter reduction, 32% WCET improvement, and 97.5% accuracy with 100% deadline compliance across 10,000 consecutive frames.

Key words Real-time systems, OCR, edge computing, WCET analysis, embedded vision.

1 Introduction

Autonomous delivery robots navigating warehouses must read shelf labels while moving at 1.2 m/s, requiring vision processing within 50 ms per frame [15]. Manufacturing inspection systems processing 30 components per second need consistent 33 ms frame processing [16]. Modern CRNN-based OCR systems [1] achieve 98% accuracy but exhibit latencies ranging 45–142 ms ($3\times$ variance) depending on text length, font complexity, and thermal state [14].

Related work. Prior work on real-time DNN inference [2,3] focuses on average-case speedup without WCET bounds. Resolution adaptation [4] reduces average latency but lacks formal timing analysis required for safety-critical certification [17]. Static WCET tools (aiT, Chronos) do not support GPU inference or data-dependent recurrent networks; measurement-based analysis [5,6] represents current best practice for ML systems.

RT-OCR addresses this gap through three contributions: (1) a *timing-aware pipeline* decomposing OCR into five stages with analyzable WCET bounds via SIMD

optimization, fixed memory allocation, and quantization-aware inference [7]; (2) an *adaptive workload controller* dynamically adjusting model precision (INT8/INT4) and resolution (64×512 , 48×384 , 32×256) to maintain deadline compliance while maximizing accuracy; (3) comprehensive *WCET characterization* covering 10,000 adversarial inputs validated on Jetson Nano and Raspberry Pi 5.

2 System Architecture

RT-OCR decomposes OCR into five sequential stages following real-time design principles [8]. Figure 1 illustrates the pipeline with per-stage WCET bounds.

Figure 1. RT-OCR pipeline with per-stage WCET (Jetson Nano, High mode). Total: 43.5 ms < 50 ms deadline.

Preprocessing (3.2 ms WCET) performs resizing to fixed 64×512 , grayscale conversion, histogram equalization, and binarization using SIMD intrinsics. Fixed resolution ensures uniform latency regardless of input content. **Inference** (38.5 ms WCET) executes a quantized CRNN forward pass; INT8 quantization reduces memory footprint 75% and latency $2.1 \times$ while retaining 98.8% accuracy [7]. Fixed batch size 1, pinned GPU frequency, and pre-allocated tensors eliminate jitter [18]. **Post-processing** (1.8 ms WCET) applies CTC decoding [9] via greedy beam search with bounded iterations.

The **adaptive workload controller** monitors inter-frame latency and selects among three modes. Downgrades are immediate; upgrades require 3 consecutive frames above the slack threshold (hysteresis) to prevent oscillation:

$$H \rightarrow M : s_k < 10 \text{ ms}, \quad M \rightarrow L : s_k < 5 \text{ ms}, \quad M \rightarrow H : s_k > 20 \text{ ms (3 fr.)}, \quad L \rightarrow M : s_k > 15 \text{ ms (3 fr.)}$$

where $s_k = D - t_k$ is the deadline slack and $D = 50 \text{ ms}$. Table 1 summarizes the three modes.

RT-OCR runs atop Linux 5.15 with PREEMPT_RT [10]: SCHED_FIFO priority 99, CPU affinity via `cpuset` cgroups, and wait-free ring buffers eliminating mutex contention.

Table 1. Operational modes of the adaptive controller.

Mode	Resolution / Precision	WCET	Accuracy
High	64×512 / INT8	38.5 ms	97.5%
Medium	48×384 / INT8	24.2 ms	96.8%
Low	32×256 / INT4	15.8 ms	94.1%

3 Experimental Evaluation

Setup. We deploy RT-OCR on Jetson Nano (ARM Cortex-A57, 128 CUDA cores, 4 GB, 5W) and Raspberry Pi 5 (ARM Cortex-A76, VideoCore VII, 8 GB, 10W) under Ubuntu 22.04 with PyTorch 2.0 and ONNX Runtime 1.16. The CRNN is trained on 800K SynthText samples [12] and evaluated on ICDAR 2015 [13] (4,468 samples), COCO-Text (173,589 instances), and a Synthetic Stress Test (50,000 adversarial inputs). Baselines: Tesseract 5.x [11], EasyOCR, TFLite.

Latency results. Table 2 reports statistics over 10,000 tasks. RT-OCR achieves the lowest WCET and jitter across all systems, with 73% jitter reduction versus EasyOCR and 82% versus Tesseract.

Table 2. Latency statistics on Jetson Nano (10,000 tasks). Jitter = (WCET−BCET)/ACET.

System	BCET	ACET	P95	WCET	Jitter
Tesseract 5.x	120	185	245	312	18.2%
EasyOCR	45	72	115	142	14.5%
TFLite	18	26	38	51	9.7%
RT-OCR High	32	38.2	41.8	43.5	2.6%

Accuracy results. Table 3 reports character-level accuracy. RT-OCR High achieves 97.5% on ICDAR 2015, only 0.6% below EasyOCR, which is acceptable given the 73% jitter reduction. RT-OCR Low (94.1%) remains competitive with TFLite.

Table 3. Character-level accuracy (%) across datasets.

System	ICDAR 2015	COCO-Text	Synth. Stress
Tesseract 5.x	92.3	88.1	81.4
EasyOCR	98.1	96.7	93.2
TFLite	94.2	91.5	87.6
RT-OCR High	97.5	96.2	92.7
RT-OCR Low	94.1	92.8	88.3

Deadline compliance. Validating 10,000 consecutive frames at the 50 ms deadline demonstrates 100% compliance with mean slack 6.8 ms (13.6% of deadline) and worst-case frame 43.2 ms. The P99 latency is 42.7 ms and P99.9 is 43.1 ms, confirming that the measured WCET reliably predicts deployment behavior. Table 4 summarizes compliance on both platforms.

Table 4. Deadline compliance over 10,000 consecutive frames ($D = 50$ ms).

Platform	WCET	Jitter	Compliance	Accuracy
Jetson Nano	43.5 ms	2.6%	100%	97.5%
Raspberry Pi 5	38.7 ms	2.9%	100%	97.3%

Energy. RT-OCR High consumes 5.2 W versus EasyOCR’s 8.4 W (38% savings), with 199 mJ per frame versus 605 mJ (67% reduction). Low mode drops to 36 mJ per frame.

Thermal throttling. Under sustained load at 35°C for 30 minutes, CPU frequency dropped from 1.43 to 1.19 GHz after 18 minutes. The adaptive controller compensated by transitioning to Medium mode in affected frames, maintaining 100% deadline compliance throughout.

4 Discussion

Compared to [4], RT-OCR provides formal WCET characterization, multi-dimensional adaptation (resolution *and* precision), and deadline-driven control guaranteeing 100% compliance. Many autonomous systems assign OCR as a dedicated subtask with isolated timing: warehouse robots read labels independently of navigation; inspection systems process serial numbers separately from defect detection. Measurement-based WCET is less rigorous than static analysis, but static tools (aiT, Chronos) do not support GPU inference or data-dependent networks. Our 10,000-sample adversarial profiling provides strong statistical assurance [5, 6]. The CRNN was trained on Latin-script SynthText; generalization to Arabic or domain-specific fonts requires re-profiling using our automated recalibration tools.

5 Conclusion

RT-OCR demonstrates that deep learning OCR with formal timing guarantees is achievable on commodity edge platforms. The 73% jitter reduction, 97.5% accuracy retention, 100% deadline compliance over 10,000 consecutive frames, and 67% energy reduction validate practical viability. Future work will extend to multi-task vision

pipelines and probabilistic WCET bounds via extreme-value theory. Source code, models, and profiling tools are available at URL anonymized for review.

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